

Supplementary Information

Generalized method of epistasis detection that can be applicable to heterozygous genotypes

We consider the following models:

$$Model_1 : \mathbf{y} = \mu + \sum_{i=1}^q \mathbf{Q}'_i \alpha_i + \mathbf{S}'_1 \beta_1 + \mathbf{S}'_2 \beta_2 + \mathbf{e} \quad (6)$$

$$Model_2 : \mathbf{y} = \mu + \sum_{i=1}^q \mathbf{Q}'_i \alpha_i + \mathbf{S}'_1 \beta_1 + \mathbf{S}'_2 \beta_2 + \sum_{j=1}^8 \mathbf{E}_j \beta_{2+j} + \mathbf{e} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{e} \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I})$$

$\beta_{3\sim 10}$ are the interaction effects of the alleles from the two SNPs (Table S2b). $\mathbf{Q}'_i, \mathbf{S}'_{1,2}$ are the n -dimensional genotype vectors of 2s as homozygous genotypes of Kaluheenati, 1s as heterozygous genotypes and 0s as homozygous genotypes of Hitomebore for each QTL and the two selected SNPs. $\mathbf{E}_{1\sim 8}$ are n -dimensional vectors with 1s for samples with the specific combination of alleles of selected SNPs and 0s for the rest. The other parameters are the same as in equations (1) and (2).